

Table 2. Generation mean analysis based on data from the populations P₁, P₂, F₁, F₂, BC indica, and BC japonica of the crosses Todoroki/IR43 and CT6241/IR43. ^a

Parameter ^b	Callus anther ⁻¹		Green plant callus ⁻¹	
	Todoroki/IR43	CT6241/IR43	Todoroki/IR43	CT6241/IR43
[m]	7.02* ^c	-5.11	16.29**	21.02**
[a]	20.75** ^c	9.12**	15.72**	21.46**
[d]	10.29*	20.33**	-1.58	-3.86
[axa]	13.79**	14.76**	-	-
[axd]	-	-	-17.85**	-28.19**
[dxd]	-	-	-	-
χ ² (2df)	1.20	3.70	3.90	4.10
P	0.55	0.16	0.14	0.13

^a According to the simplest model that explains the observed values. ^b [m] = mean value between parents, [a] = additive effects, [d] = dominant effects, [axa], [axd], and [dxd] interactions between additive and/or dominant effects. ^c *, ** = different from zero at p = 0.05 and 0.01, respectively.

segregate independently from the grain type. Plants combining high response to AC from the japonica parents (up to 70% callus induction and 90% green plant regeneration) and grain type from the indica parents (up to 8.7 mm long

and 2.9 mm wide) were recovered as early as in the F₂ generation and, subsequently, in the BC indica generations.

Twenty lines with high response to AC and long, slender grains were selected. We are evaluating individual pro-

genies from each selected line for its in vitro response and agronomic characteristics. Selected plants will be used as parents in crosses with plants from a recurrent selection population to develop a genetically diverse indica gene pool with increased response to AC.

Cited references

- Lentini Z, Reyes P, Martinez CP, Roca WM. 1995. Androgenesis of highly recalcitrant rice genotypes with maltose and silver nitrate. *Plant Sci.* 110:127-138.
- Miah MAA, Earle ED, Khush GS. 1985. Inheritance of callus formation ability in anther cultures of rice, *Oryza sativa* L. *Theor. Appl. Genet.* 70:113-116.
- Quimio CA, Zapata FJ. 1990. Diallel analysis of callus induction and green-plant regeneration in rice anther culture. *Crop Sci.* 30:188-192. ■

Random mating of composite populations for improving restorers in rice

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Most commercial indica hybrid rices have been developed through the wild abortive (WA) cytoplasmic male sterility (CMS) system, which involves using CMS (A), maintainer (B), and restorer (R) lines. Desirable restorer lines should possess good fertility restoration ability, high performance, multiple disease and insect resistance, good general combining ability, high pollen production and/or dispersal, and good grain quality. Hybrid rice breeding programs continuously need these lines to breed superior hybrids.

Most hybrid rice breeders usually select R lines among elite lines bred by inbred breeding programs where crosses are generally made without considering the parents' restoration abilities. Alternatively, R lines are also developed from R × R or A × R crosses specifically made for this purpose. Thus, frequency of R lines among a group of breeding lines depends on the

Procedure used at IRRI to develop random mating composite populations for improving restorer lines.

latter's origins and pedigrees. To regularly extract a high frequency of R lines, two random mating composite populations of restorers were developed by exercising male sterility-facilitated recurrent selection.

The procedure (see figure) involves

1. Developing a base population derived from the crosses of a genic male sterile line with a series of selected restorer lines (steps 1-4).
2. Random mating of male sterile plants with the pollen from fertile plants occurring in the base and subsequently derived populations until both male sterile and fertile plants are in equilibrium (steps 5-8).
3. Evaluating the random mating population and selecting desirable fertile plants to extract improved restorer lines, and then selecting desirable male sterile plants to form a new random mating population (step 9).

Following the procedure, two random mating composite populations of restorers were constituted at IRRI. The first population (IR69701 CP138) was derived from nine early-maturing (less than 120 d) elite restorer lines and IR36 (ms) and the second population (IR69702 CP139) was derived from 14 medium-maturing (120-140 d) elite restorer lines and IR29723-143-3-2-1 (ms) (see table). The two ms lines used were in the genetic background of restorers.

During the 1995 dry season, we reached step 8 of the procedure, in which the populations showed equilibrium among fertile and sterile plants. These populations are being used as a source for extracting genetically diverse improved restorer lines for WA CMS in rice. We are sharing seeds of these composite populations with scientists in national agricultural research systems to help them extract genetically diverse R lines for their local hybrid rice breeding programs.

During the 1995 wet season and 1996 dry season, we selected about 300

Component lines of early-maturing random-mating composite restorer population (IR69701 CP 138) and medium-maturing random-mating composite restorer population (IR69702 CP 139) and their salient features.

Component line	Salient features ^a
<i>IR69701 CP 138</i>	
IR36 ms	Genic male sterile, resistant to multiple diseases and insects, widely adapted
IR64R	High yielding, good grain quality, and resistant to major diseases and insects
IR66R	High yielding, resistant to tungro virus and BPH biotype 4
IR72R	High yielding, resistant to major diseases and insects, widely adapted
IR9761-19-1R	High pollen producer, good general combiner
IR19058-107-1R	High yielding, resistant to BPH and BB
IR44675-101-3-3-2-2R	Resistant to BPH, GLH, and BB
IR47310-94-4-3-1R	High yielding, resistant to major diseases and insects
Milyang 46R	Elite Indica/Japonica derivative line originating in Republic of Korea, good general combiner
LA2877-2-7	Long anthers derived from <i>O. sativa/O. longistaminata</i>
<i>IR69702 CP 139</i>	
IR29723-143-3-2-1 ms	Genic male sterile, high yielding, good general combiner
IR32809-26-3-3R	Resistant to BPH, cold tolerant, good general combiner
IR34686-179-12-1R	Resistant to major diseases and insects, tolerant of cold and salinity
IR40750-82-2-2-3R	Good general combiner and resistant to several diseases and insects
IR54055-142-2-1-2-3R	Resistant to BPH, GLH, and BB
IR54742-22-19-3R	Elite line derived from <i>O. sativa/O. officinalis</i>
IR54959-41-2-2R	Resistant to BPH, GLH, and BB
IR55628-79-1-3-3-3R	Resistant to GLH
IR24R	High yielding, good general combiner, possesses broad spectrum of restoration ability
IR46R	High yielding, good general combiner, also adaptable to favorable rainfed lowland ecosystem
IR64R	High yielding, good grain quality, and resistant to major diseases and insects
IR70R	Resistant to major diseases and insects
ITA121	Elite line introduced from IITA, adapted to irrigated ecosystems in West Africa
LA1451-5R	Long anther derived from <i>O. sativa/O. longistaminata</i>
LA2827-2-7R	Long anther derived from <i>O. sativa/O. longistaminata</i>

^a BPH = brown planthopper; GLH = green leafhopper; BB = bacterial blight.

single plants from these populations at IRRI. We are now evaluating these in a pedigree nursery. The promising R lines identified can again be made into

composites by repeating this procedure, thus developing new random mating composite populations for further improving R lines. ■

Yield potential

Influence of brassinosteroid on rice seedling growth

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Since brassinosteroid (BR) was discovered as a new family of plant hormones, scientists have recognized its importance in regulating plant growth and reproduction. BR and its analogues have been synthesized or isolated and are available to biologists for basic physiological and biochemical studies

and field experiments. BR has been isolated in rice plants.

Seeds of hybrid rice variety D You 63 and conventional variety Fujiang 2 were surface-sterilized, rinsed in sterile water, and then dried with blotting paper. BR, which was isolated from beeswax, was dissolved with a little alcohol and then diluted with distilled water to various concentrations. Seeds were pre-soaked in different concentrations of BR or distilled water (as a control). Imbibed seeds were placed in 30- × 20-cm plastic culture pans. Nutrient solution was added when the first true leaf emerged.